

ABOUT THE SMARANDACHE COMPLEMENTARY PRIME FUNCTION

by

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Let $c : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ be the function defined by the condition that $n + c(n) = p_i$, where p_i is the smallest prime number, $p_i \geq n$.

Example

$c(0) = 2, c(1) = 1, c(2) = 0, c(3) = 0, c(4) = 1, c(5) = 0, c(6) = 1,$
 $c(7) = 0$ and so on.

1) If p_k and p_{k-1} are two consecutive primes and $p_k < n \leq p_{k-1}$, then :

$c(n) \in \{ p_{k-1} - p_k - 1, p_{k-1} - p_k - 2, \dots, 1, 0 \}$, because :

$c(p_k + 1) = p_{k-1} - p_k - 1$ and so on, $c(p_{k-1}) = 0$.

2) $c(p) = c(p-1) - 1 = 0$ for every p prime, because $c(p) = 0$ and $c(p-1) = 1$.

We also can observe that $c(n) \neq c(n+1)$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

1. Property

The equation $c(n) = n, n > 1$ has no solutions.

Proof

If n is a prime it results $c(n) = 0 < n$.

It is wellknown that between n and $2n, n > 1$ there exists at least a prime number. Let p_k be the smallest prime of them. Then if n is a composite number we have :

$c(n) = p_k - n < 2n - n = n$, therefore $c(n) < n$.

It results that for every $n \neq p$, where p is a prime, we have $\frac{1}{n} \leq \frac{c(n)}{n} < 1$, therefore $\sum_{\substack{n \neq p \\ p \text{ prime}}} \frac{c(n)}{n}$ diverges. Because for the primes $c(p)/p = 0$ we can say that $\sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{c(n)}{n}$ diverges.

2. Property

If n is a composite number, then $c(n) = c(n-1) - 1$.

Proof

Obviously.

It results that for n and $(n+1)$ composite numbers we have $\frac{c(n)}{c(n+1)} > 1$. Now, if $p_k < n < p_{k+1}$ where p_k and p_{k+1} are consecutive primes, then we have :

$$c(n) c(n+1) \dots c(p_{k+1} - 1) = (p_{k+1} - n)!$$

$$\text{and if } n \leq p_k < p_{k+1} \text{ then } c(n) c(n+1) \dots c(p_{k+1} - 1) = 0.$$

Of course, every $\prod_{n=k}^r c(n) = 0$ if there exists a prime number p , $k \leq p \leq r$.

If $n = p_k$ is any prime number, then $c(n) = 0$ and because $c(n+1) = p_{k+1} - n - 1$ it results that $|c(n) - c(n+1)| = 1$ if and only if n and $(n+2)$ are primes (friend prime numbers)

3. Property

For every k -th prime number p_k we have :

$$c(p_k + 1) < (\log p_k)^2 - 1.$$

Proof

Because $c(p_k + 1) = p_{k+1} - p_k - 1$ we have $p_{k+1} - p_k = c(p_k + 1) + 1$.

But, on the other hand we have $p_{k+1} - p_k < (\log p_k)^2$, then the assertion follows.

4. Property

$c(c(n)) < c(n)$ and $c^m(n) < c(n) < n$, for every $n > 1$ and $m \geq 2$.

Proof

If we denote $c(n) = r$ then we have :

$$c(c(n)) = c(r) < r = c(n).$$

Then we suppose that the assertion is true for m : $c^m(n) < c(n) < n$, and we prove it

for $(m - 1)$, too :

$$c^{m-1}(n) = c(c^m(n)) < c^m(n) < c(n) < n.$$

5. Property

For every prime p we have $(c(p - 1))^n \leq c((p - 1)^n)$.

Proof

$c(p - 1) = 1 \Rightarrow (c(p - 1))^n = 1$ while $(p - 1)^n$ is a composite number, therefore $c((p - 1)^n) \geq 1$.

6. Property

The following kind of Fibonacci equation :

$$c(n) - c(n - 1) = c(n + 2) \tag{1}$$

has solutions.

Proof

If n and $(n + 1)$ are both composite numbers, then $c(n) > c(n + 1) \geq 1$. If $(n + 2)$ is a prime, then $c(n + 2) = 0$ and we have no solutions in this case. If $(n + 2)$ is also a composite number, then :

$$c(n) > c(n + 1) > c(n + 2) \geq 1, \text{ therefore } c(n) + c(n + 1) > c(n + 2)$$

and we have no solutions also in this case.

Therefore n and $(n + 1)$ are not both composite numbers in the equality (1).

If n is a prime, then $(n + 1)$ is a composite number and we must have :

$$0 - c(n + 1) = c(n + 2), \text{ wich is not possible (see (2)).}$$

We have only the case when $(n + 1)$ is a prime; in this case we must have :

$1 - 0 = c(n + 2)$ but this implies that $(n + 3)$ is a prime number, so the only solutions are when $(n + 1)$ and $(n + 2)$ are friend prime numbers.

7. Property

The following equation:

$$\frac{c(n) + c(n + 2)}{2} = c(n + 1) \tag{2}$$

has an infinite number of solutions.

Proof

Let p_k and p_{k-1} be two consecutive prime numbers, but not friend prime numbers.

Then, for every integer i between $p_k + 1$ and $p_{k-1} - 1$ we have:

$$\frac{c(i-1) + c(i+1)}{2} = \frac{(p_{k+1} - i + 1) + (p_{k+1} - i - 1)}{2} = p_{k+1} - i = c(i).$$

So, for the equation (2) all positive integer n between $p_k + 1$ and $p_{k-1} - 1$ is a solution.

If n is prime, the equation becomes $\frac{c(n+2)}{2} = c(n+1)$.

But $(n+1)$ is a composite number, therefore $c(n+1) \neq 0 \Rightarrow c(n+2)$ must be composite number. Because in this case $c(n+1) = c(n+2) + 1$ and the equation has the form $\frac{c(n+2)}{2} = c(n+2) + 1$, so we have no solutions.

If $(n+1)$ is prime, then we must have $\frac{c(n) + c(n+2)}{2} = 0$, where n and $(n+2)$ are composite numbers. So we have no solutions in this case, because $c(n) \geq 1$ and $c(n+2) \geq 1$.

If $(n+2)$ is a prime, the equation has the form $\frac{c(n)}{2} = c(n+1)$, where $(n+1)$ is a composite number, therefore $c(n+1) \neq 0$. From (2) it results that $c(n) \neq 0$, so n is also a composite number. This case is the same with the first considered case.

Therefore the only solutions are for $\overline{p_k, p_{k+1} - 2}$, where p_k, p_{k-1} are consecutive primes, but not friend consecutive primes.

8. Property

The greatest common divisor of n and $c(x)$ is 1 :

$(x, c(x)) = 1$, for every composite number x .

Proof

Taking into account of the definition of the function c , we have $x + c(x) = p$, where p is a prime number.

If there exists $d \neq 1$ so that d / x and $d / c(x)$, then it implies that d / p . But p is a prime number, therefore $d = p$.

This is not possible because $c(x) < p$.

If p is a prime number, then $(p, c(p)) = (p, 0) = p$.

9. Property

The equation $[x, y] = [c(x), c(y)]$, where $[x, y]$ is the least common multiple of x and y has no solutions for $x, y > 1$.

Proof

Let us suppose that $x = dk_1$ and $y = dk_2$, where $d = (x, y)$. Then we must have :

$$[x, y] = dk_1 k_2 = [c(x), c(y)].$$

But $(x, c(x)) = (dk_1, c(x)) = 1$, therefore dk_1 is given in the least common multiple $[c(x), c(y)]$ by $c(y)$.

$$\text{But } (y, c(y)) = (dk_2, c(y)) = 1 \Rightarrow d = 1 \Rightarrow (x, y) = 1 \Rightarrow$$

$\Rightarrow [x, y] = xy > c(x)c(y) \geq [c(x), c(y)]$, therefore the above equation has no solutions. for $x, y > 1$.

For $x = 1 = y$ we have $[x, y] = [c(x), c(y)] = 1$.

10. Property

The equation :

$$(x, y) = (c(x), c(y)) \quad (3)$$

has an infinite number of solutions.

Proof

If $x = 1$ and $y = p - 1$ then $(x, y) = 1$ and $(c(x), c(y)) = (1, 1) = 1$, for an arbitrary prime p .

Easily we observe that every pair $(n, n + 1)$ of numbers is a solutions for the equation (3), if n is not a prime.

11. Property

The equation :

$$c(x) + x = c(y) + y \quad (4)$$

has an infinite number of solutions.

Proof

From the definition of the function c it results that for every x and y satisfying

$p_k < x \leq y \leq p_{k+1}$ we have $c(x) + x = c(y) + y = p_{k+1}$. Therefore we have $(p_{k+1} - p_k)^2$ couples (x, y) as different solutions. Then, until the n -th prime p_n , we have $\sum_{k=1}^{n-1} (p_{k+1} - p_k)^2$ different solutions.

Remark

It seems that the equation $c(x) + y = c(y) + x$ has no solutions $x \neq y$, but it is not true.

Indeed, let p_k and p_{k+1} be consecutive primes such that $p_{k+1} - p_k = 6$ (is possible: for example $29 - 23 = 6$, $37 - 31 = 6$, $53 - 47 = 6$ and so on) and $p_k - 2$ is not a prime.

Then $c(p_k - 2) = 2$, $c(p_k - 1) = 1$, $c(p_k) = 0$, $c(p_k + 1) = 5$, $c(p_k + 2) = 4$, $c(p_k + 3) = 3$ and we have:

1. $c(p_k + 1) - c(p_k - 2) = 5 - 2 = 3 = (p_k + 1) - (p_k - 2)$
2. $c(p_k + 2) - c(p_k - 1) = 4 - 1 = 3 = (p_k + 2) - (p_k - 1)$
3. $c(p_k + 3) - c(p_k) = 3 - 0 = 3 = (p_k + 3) - p_k$, thus

$c(x) - c(y) = x - y \Leftrightarrow c(x) + y = c(y) + x$ has the above solutions if $p_k - p_{k-1} > 3$

If $p_k - p_{k-1} = 2$ we have only the two last solutions.

In the general case, when $p_{k+1} - p_k = 2h$, $h \in \mathbb{N}^*$, let $x = p_k - u$ and $y = p_k + v$, $u, v \in \mathbb{N}$ be the solutions of the above equation.

Then $c(x) = c(p_k - u) = u$ and $c(y) = c(p_k + v) = 2h - v$.

The equation becomes:

$u + (p_k + v) = (2h - v) + (p_k - u)$, thus $u + v = h$.

Therefore, the solutions are $x = p_k - u$ and $y = p_k + h - u$, for every $u = \overline{0, h}$ if $p_k - p_{k-1} > h$ and $x = p_k - u$, $y = p_k + h - u$, for every $u = \overline{0, l}$ if $p_k - p_{k-1} = l + 1 \leq h$.

Remark

$c(p_k + 1)$ is an odd number, because if p_k and p_{k+1} are consecutive primes, $p_k > 2$, then p_k and p_{k+1} are, of course, odd numbers; then $p_{k+1} - p_k - 1 = c(p_k + 1)$ are **always** odd.

12. Property

The sumatory function of c , $F_c(n) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{\substack{d \in \mathbb{N} \\ d|n}} c(d)$ has the properties:

$$a) F_c(2p) = 1 + c(2p)$$

$$b) F_c(pq) = 1 + c(pq), \text{ where } p \text{ and } q \text{ are prime numbers.}$$

Proof

$$a) F_c(2p) = c(1) + c(2) + c(p) + c(2p) = 1 + c(2p).$$

$$b) F_c(pq) = c(1) + c(p) + c(q) + c(pq) = 1 + c(pq).$$

Remark

The function c is not multiplicative : $0 = c(2) \cdot c(p) < c(2p)$.

13. Property

$$c^k(p) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } k \text{ odd number} \\ 2 & \text{for } k \text{ even number, } k \geq 1 \end{cases}$$

Proof

We have :

$$c^1(p) = 0;$$

$$c^2(p) = c(c(p)) = c(0) = 2;$$

$$c^3(p) = c(2) = 0;$$

$$c^4(p) = c(0) = 2.$$

Using the complete mathematical induction, the property holds.

Consequences

$$1) \text{ We have } \frac{c^k(p) + c^{k+1}(p)}{2} = 1 \text{ for every } k \geq 1 \text{ and } p \text{ prime number.}$$

$$2) \sum_{k=1}^r c^k(p) = \left[\frac{r}{2} \right] \cdot 2, \text{ where } [x] \text{ is the integer part of } x, \text{ and}$$

$$\sum_{\substack{k=2 \\ k \text{ even}}}^r \frac{1}{c^k(p)} = \left[\frac{r}{2} \right] \cdot \frac{1}{2}, \text{ thus } \sum_{k \geq 1} c^k(p) \text{ and } \sum_{\substack{k \geq 2 \\ k \text{ even}}} \frac{1}{c^k(p)} \text{ are divergent series.}$$

Remark

$$c^k(p-1) = c^{k-1}(c(p-1)) = c^{k-1}(1) = 1, \text{ for every prime } p > 3 \text{ and } k \in \mathbb{N}^*,$$

therefore $c^{k_1}(p_1-1) = c^{k_2}(p_2-1)$ for every primes $p_1, p_2 > 3$ and $k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{N}^*$.

14. Property

The equation :

$$c(x) + c(y) + c(z) = c(x)c(y)c(z) \quad (5)$$

has an infinite number of solutions.

Proof

The only non-negative solutions for the diofantine equation $a + b + c = abc$ are $a = 1$, $b = 2$ and $c = 3$ and all circular permutations of $\{ 1, 2, 3 \}$.

Then :

$$c(x) = 1 \Rightarrow x = p_k - 1, p_k \text{ prime number, } p_k > 3$$

$$c(y) = 2 \Rightarrow y = p_k - 2, \text{ where } p_{r-1} \text{ and } p_r \text{ are consecutive prime numbers such}$$

that $p_r - p_{r-1} \geq 3$

$$c(z) = 3 \Rightarrow z = p_i - 3, \text{ where } p_{i-1} \text{ and } p_i \text{ are consecutive prime numbers such that}$$

$$p_i - p_{i-1} \geq 4$$

and all circular permutations of the above values of x, y and z .

Of course, the equation $c(x) = c(y)$ has an infinite number of solutions.

Remark

We can consider $c^{\leftarrow}(y)$, for every $y \in \mathbb{N}^*$, defined as $c^{\leftarrow}(y) = \{ x \in \mathbb{N} \mid c(x) = y \}$.

For example $c^{\leftarrow}(0)$ is the set of all primes, and $c^{\leftarrow}(1)$ is the set $\{ 1, p_{k-1} \}_{p_k \text{ prime}}$ and so on.
 $p_k > 3$

A study of these sets may be interesting.

Remark

If we have the equation :

$$c^k(x) = c(y), k \geq 2 \tag{6}$$

then, using property 13, we have two cases.

If x is prime and k is odd, then $c^k(x) = 0$ and (5) implies that y is prime.

In the case when x is prime and k is even it results $c^k(x) = 2 = c(y)$, which implies that y is a prime, such that $y - 2$ is not prime.

If $x = p, y = q, p$ and q primes, $p, q > 3$, then $(p - 1, q - 1)$ are also solutions, because $c^k(p - 1) = 1 = c(q - 1)$, so the above equation has an infinite number of couples as solutions.

Also a study of $(c^k(x))^{\leftarrow}$ seems to be interesting.

Remark

The equation :

$$c(n) + c(n-1) + c(n+2) = c(n-1) \quad (7)$$

has solutions when $c(n-1) = 3$, $c(n) = 2$, $c(n+1) = 1$, $c(n+2) = 0$, so the solutions are $n = p - 2$ for every p prime number such that between $p - 4$ and p there is not another prime.

The equation :

$$c(n-2) + c(n-1) + c(n+1) + c(n+2) = 4c(n) \quad (8)$$

has as solutions $n = p - 3$, where p is a prime such that between $p - 6$ and p there is not another prime, because $4c(n) = 12$ and $c(n-2) + c(n-1) + c(n+1) + c(n+2) = 12$.

For example $n = 29 - 3 = 26$ is a solution of the equation (7).

The equation :

$$c(n) + c(n-1) + c(n-2) + c(n-3) + c(n-4) = 2c(n-5) \quad (9)$$

(see property 7) has as solution $n = p - 5$, where p is a prime, such that between $p - 6$ and p there is not another prime. Indeed we have $0 + 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 = 2 \cdot 5$.

Thus, using the properties of the function c we can decide if an equation, which has a similar form with the above equations, has or has not solutions.

But a difficult problem is : " For any even number a , can we find consecutive primes such that $p_{k-1} - p_k = a$? "

The answer is useful to find the solutions of the above kind of equations, but is also important to give the answer in order to solve another open problem :

" Can we get, as large as we want, but finite decreasing sequence $k, k - 1, \dots, 2, 1, 0$ (**odd k**), included in the sequence of the values of c ?"

If someone gives an answer to this problem, then it is easy to give the answer (it will be the same) at the similar following problem :

" Can we get, as large as we want, but finite decreasing sequence $k, k - 1, \dots, 2, 1, 0$ (**even k**), included in the sequence of the values of c ?"

We suppose the answer is negative.

In the same order of idea, it is interesting to find $\max_n \frac{c(n)}{n}$.

It is wellknown (see [4], page 147) that $p_{n+1} - p_n < (\ln p_n)^2$, where p_n and p_{n+1} are two consecutive primes.

Moreover, $\frac{c(n)}{n}$, $p_k < n \leq p_{k+1}$ reaches its maximum value for $n = p_k + 1$, where p_k is a prime.

So, in this case :

$$\frac{c(n)}{n} = \frac{p_{k+1} - p_k - 1}{p_k + 1} < \frac{(\ln p_k)^2 - 1}{p_k + 1} \xrightarrow{k \rightarrow \infty} 0$$

Using this result, we can find the maximum value of $\frac{c(n)}{n}$

$$\text{For } p > 100 \text{ we have } \frac{(\ln p)^2 - 1}{p + 1} < \frac{(\ln 100)^2 - 1}{101} < \frac{1}{4}$$

Using the computer, by a straight forward computation, it is easy to prove that

$$\max_{2 \leq n \leq 100} \frac{c(n)}{n} = \frac{3}{8}, \text{ which is reached for } n = 8.$$

$$\text{Because } \frac{c(n)}{n} < \frac{1}{4} \text{ for every } n > 100 \text{ it results that } \max_{n \geq 2} \frac{c(n)}{n} = \frac{3}{8}$$

reached for $n = 8$.

Remark

There exists an infinite number of finite sequences $\{ c(k_1), c(k_1 + 1), \dots, c(k_2) \}$ such that $\sum_{k=k_1}^{k_2} c(k)$ is a three-cornered number for $k_1, k_2 \in \mathbb{N}^*$ (the n -th three-cornered number is $T_n \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \frac{n(n+1)}{2}$, $n \in \mathbb{N}^*$).

For example, in the case $k_1 = p_k$ and $k_2 = p_{k+1}$, two consecutive primes, we have the

finite sequence $\{ c(p_k), c(p_k + 1), \dots, c(p_{k+1} - 1), c(p_{k+1}) \}$ and

$$\sum_{k=p_k}^{p_{k+1}} c(k) = 0 + (p_{k+1} - p_k - 1) + \dots + 2 + 1 + 0 = \frac{(p_{k+1} - p_k - 1)(p_{k+1} - p_k)}{2} = T_{p_{k+1} - p_k - 1}$$

Of course, we can define the function $c' : \mathbb{N} \setminus \{ 0, 1 \} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, $c'(n) = n - k$, where k is the smallest natural number such that $n - k$ is a prime number, but we shall give some properties of this function in another paper.

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